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GEOCHEMICAL ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF MINING - METALLURGICAL WASTES AND ALKALI ACTIVATING MATERIALS

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Introduction

The urgent need for critical raw materials (CRMs), extracted in most cases as by-products from low-grade ores, is expected to result in the production of large volumes of mining and metallurgical wastes, including mine overburden, beneficiation tailings, wastes from tailings re-mining, as well as leaching residues and metallurgical slags. These wastes, if improperly handled, may result in the release and transfer of potentially harmful elements (PHEs) into environmental receptors, namely air, soil and water¹. Various options are available for the valorisation / treatment of these wastes and the minimisation of their toxicity. Alkali activation is an alternative and relatively low-cost technique, which results in the production of secondary materials, often called alkali-activated materials (AAMs) or inorganic polymers or geopolymers. It has also the potential to stabilise most PHEs present in the starting materials^{2,3}. The present study aims to provide some insights on the mobility of PHEs present in metallurgical slags as well as in silicate and ilmenite tailings and the subsequently produced AAMs by using different standard tests. It aims also to trigger discussions about the suitability and reliability of each test for such wastes.

Materials and Methods

In this study five different samples of slags and tailings were evaluated. LS and ENS are slags produced from the treatment of laterites in FeNi production plants in Greece and N. Macedonia, respectively. Both slags are partially amorphous and mainly contain fayalite, diopside, olivine and magnetite. BOHA is fayalitic slag (the main phase is fayalite) produced from the pyrometallurgical processing of Ni/Co concentrates at Boliden Harjavalta, Finland. KST are low-sulphur silicate tailings produced after pyrite flotation at Kevitsa, Finland; the main mineralogical phases are amphibole, plagioclase, diopside, chlorite, olivine and serpentine. OTA are tailings produced after gravitational and magnetic separation of Fe-Ti-V oxide ores from Otanmäki mine, Finland; the main mineralogical phases are magnesio-hornblende, ilmenite, muscovite and chlorite. Prior to alkali activation all raw materials were ground to below 100 µm. The d₉₀ of all samples varied between 28.1 µm for KST and 83.3 µm for OTA. For the production of

AAMs, the ground raw materials were mixed with the activating solution, consisting of 8 mol/L NaOH and Na₂SiO₃ (7.5-8.5 wt% Na₂O and 25.5-28.5 wt% SiO₂) solutions, in a laboratory mixer for about 10 min. A typical average indicative composition of the starting mixture is (in wt%): solids 81%, 8M NaOH solution 9% and Na₂SiO₃ solution 9%. The liquid to solid (L/S) ratio varied from 0.2 to 0.3, depending on the raw material used. The resulting paste was cast into 5 cm edge cubic moulds, which were vibrated for 3 minutes to eliminate air voids. After 24 h, the hardened specimens were demoulded, sealed in plastic bags to avoid fast evaporation of water and oven-cured at 80 °C for 24 h. More curing regimes were examined however, the results provided in this paper refer to specimens produced from these conditions. Then, specimens were left for aging in the laboratory (~20 °C) for 7 days and the compressive strength, as well as other properties (not shown in this paper) were determined. The leaching of PHEs from the three slags (LS, BOHA, ENS), the silicate (KST) and ilmenite tailings (OTA) as well as the respective AAMs, produced from the alkali activation of the five by-product / waste types, was assessed with the use of different leaching tests, namely EN 12457-2⁴, Toxicity Characteristic Leaching Procedure (TCLP)⁵, and NEN 7341⁶. The concentration of all elements in solution was determined through AAS or ICP-OES.

Results

The chemical analyses of the raw materials, as derived by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) in the form of oxides, is shown in Table 1. Loss-on-ignition (LOI) was 2.1 wt% for KST, 3.7 wt% for OTA and very low for the slags (<0.2 wt%).

Table 1: Chemical analysis of raw materials (wt%)

Oxide	LS	ENS	BOHA	KST	OTA	Oxide	LS	ENS	BOHA	KST	OTA
SiO ₂	33.6	37.8	30.9	44.7	22.1	SO ₃	0.3	0.3	0.6	1.8	0.6
Al ₂ O ₃	8.3	4.3	2.9	4.0	12.2	TiO ₂	0.7	0.2	0.3	0.4	13.7
MgO	6.4	17.4	8.5	21.8	8.4	NiO	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.01
Fe ₂ O ₃	39.6	31.5	52.3	11.5	50.1	CuO	0.002	0.003	0.2	0.04	0.01
CaO	5.6	4.7	2.4	13.5	6.0	ZnO	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.04
Cr ₂ O ₃	2.9	2.3	0.2	0.3	0.01						

Figure 1(a,b) show the leached concentration of Ni for all raw materials (except OTA) and the produced AAMs as determined from the use of EN 12457-2, NEN 7341 and TCLP tests. It is seen that for the EN 12457-2 test the leached concentration of Ni is for all raw materials well below the threshold of 10 mg/kg, so they can be disposed at landfills for non-hazardous wastes. NEN 7341 indicates increased concentration of Ni in the leachates for all slags, between 12 and 32 mg/kg, however no threshold values exist for this test that was withdrawn from the Dutch legislation in 2015. The TCLP test indicates also increased leached concentrations for Ni for all samples, between 6-16 mg/L,

however also no threshold values exist for Ni in this test. This increased TCLP mobility of Ni is mainly due to the lower pH of the test. On the other hand, it is seen that the leaching rate of Ni from the produced AAMs is drastically reduced, indicating that alkali activation of all materials results in the development of a strong solidified matrix that does not easily allow the release of the encapsulated elements. Quite similar results derive also for the other 3 elements, namely Cr, Cu and Zn. It is also seen that the leached concentration of all three metals is well below the EN 12457-2 limits, while no limits are indicated for these metals (except for Cr, 5 mg/L) for the TCLP test. It is underlined that the compressive strength of the produced AAMs varies between max. 132 MPa (for the LS AAM) and min. 22 MPa (for the KST AAM). Finally, Figure 5 shows the leached concentrations of Ni, Zn, Cr and Cu from OTA tailings as derived from the use of EN 12457-2 and TCLP tests. It is seen that in this case the leached concentration of Ni and Zn exceed the EN 12457-2 for acceptance in landfills of non-hazardous wastes, while the concentrations for Cu and Cr are well below the respective limits.

Figure 1: Leached conc. of Ni as determined from the use of 3 tests, (a) raw materials and (b) AAMs. For the EN 12457-2 and NEN 7341 tests the values are mg/kg, while for TCLP in mg/L. The solid red horizontal line is the EN 12457-2 Ni limit for non hazardous wastes

Figure 2: Leached conc. of Cr as determined from the use of 3 tests, (a) raw materials and (b) AAMs. The red solid horizontal line is the EN 12457-2 Cr limit for non hazardous wastes

Figure 3: Leached concentrations of Cu as determined from the use of 3 tests, (a) raw materials and (b) AAMs. The red solid horizontal line is the EN12457-2 Cu limit for non hazardous wastes

Figure 4: Leached concentrations of Zn as determined with the use of 3 tests; (a) raw materials and (b) AAMs. The red solid horizontal line is the EN 12457-2 Zn limit for non hazardous wastes

Figure 5: Leached concentrations of Ni, Zn, Cr and Cu from OTA tailings as determined from the use of EN 12457-2 and TCLP tests. Horizontal lines are the EN12457-2 Zn, Cu, Ni and Cr limits for non hazardous wastes

The differences in the leached concentrations of the studied heavy metals in the three tests and the final assessment of each waste / AAM are due to the conditions prevailing in each test (e.g lower pH in the TCLP test, high L/S ratio (50:1) in NEN, different grain size / specific surface area of each waste and also different indicated limits). The results of these tests may be compared also with the results of the sequential extraction procedure⁷ that evaluates the actual and potential mobilisation of metal(oids) under typical environmental conditions (results not shown in this paper).

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